

ISic1366

I.Sicily inscription 1366

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140871

1. ἐνθάδ[ε κῖ]-

2. τε Π[ρ]ιμ [ιγένιος]

3. ὑποδ [ιάκονος]

4. κὲ θυρ[ωρός].

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492980

EDCS 39101746

PHI 140871

Bibliography

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